

HeatResilientCity II - work package 2.2: Influence of regional and urban climate on indoor overheating – Building models, simulation boundary condition and their variations

Naming convention for building models

BUILDING_LOCATION_YEAR_URBCLIM_VERSION_ADD

BUILDING: simulated building model (GZH or LPC)

LOCATION: considered region/city

- DD for Dresden
- HH for Hamburg
- K for Köln
- S for Stuttgart
- P for Potsdam

YEAR: considered weather dataset

- TYPJJJJ
 - o JJJJ indicates the selected year from the weather station data of the climate normal from 1991 to 2020
 - o TYP (Test Year Present) indicates that the selected year (from the climate normal 1991 - 2020) represents an average **present** summer
- TYFJJJJ
 - o JJJJ indicates the selected year from the weather station data of the climate normal from 1991 to 2020
 - o TYF (Test Year Future) indicates that the selected year (from the climate normal 1991 - 2020) represents an average present **future** summer
- If YEAR is equals to 'TRY2010-04-Jahr' or 'TRY2010-12-Jahr' the designation stands for the Test Reference Year according to DIN 4108-2 (DIN, 2013)

URBCLIM: information if urban climate is considered

- URBCLIM = nUHI, if not considered (climate data from weather station not further modified)
- URBCLIM = UHI, if considered (temperature, relative humidity and windspeed are modified in the climate data from the weather station)

VERSION: information about changes in building model e. g. adaptation measures

- A1.10 Basic model for GZH building
- B1.10 Heat adapted model for GZH building with adaptation measure AM 1
- B2.10 Heat adapted model for GZH building with adaptation measure AM 2
- B3.10 Heat adapted model for GZH building with adaptation measure AM 3

- E1.10.....Basic model for LPC building
- F1.10.....Heat adapted model for LPC building with adaptation measure AM 1
- F2.10.....Heat adapted model for LPC building with adaptation measure AM 2
- F3.10.....Heat adapted model for LPC building with adaptation measure AM 3

ADD: additional information if required

Naming convention for climate data

The climate data files follow the naming convention of the building models, but they are extended by the information of the coordinates of the associated weather station.

LOCATION_YEAR_URBCLIM_LAT_LONG_VERSION

LOCATION: considered region/city

- DD for Dresden
- HH for Hamburg
- K for Köln
- S for Stuttgart
- P for Potsdam
- Empty for TRY

YEAR: considered weather dataset

- TYPJJJJ
 - o JJJJ indicates the selected year from the measurement data of the climate normal from 1991 to 2020
 - o TYP (Test Year Present) indicates that the selected year (from the climate normal 1991 - 2020) represents an average **present** summer
- TYFJJJJ
 - o JJJJ indicates the selected year from the measurement data of the climate normal from 1991 to 2020
 - o TYF (Test Year Future) indicates that the selected year (from the climate normal 1991 - 2020) represents an average present **future** summer
- If YEAR is equals to 'TRY2010-04-Jahr' or 'TRY2010-12-Jahr' the designation stands for the Test Reference Year according to DIN 4108-2 (DIN, 2013)

LAT: Latitude of associated weather station

LONG: Longitude of associated weather station

VERSION: Version extension.

Literature and related data

DIN, 2013. DIN 4108-2:2013-02, Wärmeschutz und Energie-Einsparung in Gebäuden Teil 2: Mindestanforderungen an den Wärmeschutz. Beuth Verlag, Berlin.